

NEWSLETTER

An Initiative of ISAJ

Inside This Issue

An Appeal!

Be an Organizer of ISAJ Events!

From the Editor's Desk

Research Spotlight

Photopharmacology: Shining Light for Drug Action

Research Highlight

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence-based Algorithm and AI-inspired Knowledge to Improve Material Strength.

Event Report

14th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2023

Photo Gallery

14th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2023

<http://isaj.org>

Join ISAJ as an organizer!

Join the Executive Committee!

The Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is a non-profit organization founded in 2008 to provide an organizational framework to promote greater interaction between Indian researchers working in Japan and the Japanese scientific community. ISAJ provides a platform for networking and the exchange of information, such as by organizing scientific seminars and special lectures. It includes organization of an annual ISAJ scientific symposium to help develop and strengthen research networks.

ISAJ was conceived and structured in 2008, formally inaugurated by Prof. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India on January 19, 2009). It was registered as a Non-Profit Organization (NPO) in Japan in 2010.

Since the inception of ISAJ, the Ambassador of India to Japan and Counselor of Science & Technology, the Embassy of India, Japan, have been the honorary patron and honorary advisor, respectively. ISAJ has organized six annual symposia in Tokyo, thirteen interactive lectures by the Tsukuba Chapter, and several seminars/meetings by the Tokyo Chapter and other regional chapters.

Annual Symposium of ISAJ

ISAJ has been organizing an Annual Symposium since 2010. The primary objective of the symposium is to promote interaction and exchange of ideas among Indian and Japanese scientists. Over the years, the symposium has achieved many other objectives. Foremost is providing a platform to showcase the excellent science being done by Indian researchers and their colleagues in Japan to a wider audience. The symposium often invites heads of science agencies such as JSPS and JST, as well as research and educational institutions, to witness the strength of the Indian research community in Japan.

Highly accomplished researchers in various fields of science and technology in Japan are invited to the symposium to share their expertise. It is very inspiring to listen to these talks, even for non-specialists in

those fields of science and technology. Moreover, the symposium has given the opportunity to show appreciation to those senior researchers and professors who have hosted, mentored, and nurtured Indian researchers in their laboratories.

Not the least important is the opportunity given to a large number of young Indian researchers in Japan to organize these symposia. Every year we have inducted motivated young researchers to convene the symposia by forming their own organizing committee. This endeavor works towards fulfilling our aim to bring up the leadership in our community of Indian researchers. We hope that they will lead our community in these changing times.

The symposia have been held in various locations, including the Embassy of India main auditorium, the University of Tokyo campus, the AIST auditorium in Tsukuba, Osaka University Hall, online, hybrid, Tokai University in Shizuoka, and Hokkaido University campus. With the rapidly increasing number of Indian researchers in Japan, it is now possible to organize symposia in each part of Japan (Northern, Tohoku, Kanto/Tokyo, Kansai, and Kyushu) every year.

!!!Be an organizer of ISAJ events!!! Join its executive committee!

ISAJ is a non-profit organization that aims to elevate the profile and status of the Indian researcher and academic community in Japan. A number of volunteers have made it possible to organize the various activities of ISAJ, including its annual symposium, who have come forward due to their own motivation. It has been a lot of fun working together to organize truly multidisciplinary science events.

We call upon your initiative and dedication to organize ISAJ events in your area. You can submit your proposals and ideas to the Chairman of ISAJ (s-kaul@aist.go.jp) for organizational support. We also invite you to join our organizing committee so that you can go ahead for implementing your ideas.

From Editor's Desk

Greetings and a warm welcome to this issue of ISAJ Newsletter in 2024!

In this issue, we present you with two research articles and an event report on the 14th Annual ISAJ Symposium 2023. The Research articles are on “Visible-light active heteroaryl azo photoswitches for photopharmacology” and “Utilizing the artificial intelligence-based technique to improve the material strength.” This edition also includes photographs from our 14th Annual Symposium, held near the end of the last year.

Under the Research Spotlight section, we present you an article on emerging field of photopharmacology, which lies at intersection of chemistry, biology and medicine. It explores the use of light to control the pharmacological activity of drugs. It can enable targeted, light-induced drug toxicity, presenting a future clinical translation possibility. It has diverse potential applications, such as vision restoration, combating antibiotic resistance, reducing chemotherapy side effects, and addressing diabetes.

The second research article discusses improvement in the mechanical strength of Ni-based superalloys using the artificial intelligence (AI) technique. Superalloys are used in extreme environments, such as in airplane engines and turbines, which work at high-temperatures, corrosive environment, and undergo fatigue. Increasing their strength is vital for efficiency and human safety. AI is gaining significant attention recently. The author briefly explains the working concept of the AI technique, Monte Carlo tree search (MCTS) integrated it with the Materials Integration by network technology (MInt) and predicted the strength in NiAl alloys.

ISAJ organized its 14th Annual Symposium on November 10 (Fri), 2023 in the Conference Hall, North Campus, Hokkaido University, Sapporo. The symposium theme was “Integrated Science for a Sustainable Society.” There were about 100 participants, including 3 plenary speakers, 14 invited speakers and 43 poster presenters. Eight young researchers made oral presentations besides their poster presentations.

Lastly, inside the front cover, there is an appeal, or an invitation, to be an organizer of events, be locally in your area or internationally. Write to our committee members to volunteer.

We hope you would find the present issue of our Newsletter interesting. We look forward to receiving your feedback. Any suggestions/ideas for improving the upcoming newsletters are welcome.

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Photopharmacology: Shining Light for Drug Action

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Presently working for her Ph.D at the Department of Life Science at Hokkaido University, Nusaiba received her master's degree in pharmaceutical sciences from the University of Tokyo. Her research area includes the synthesis of small molecules such as photoswitches and fluorescent sensors. Her current research focuses on the development of heteroaryl photoswitches for photopharmacology applications.

Introduction

Photopharmacology is an emerging field at the intersection of chemistry, biology, and medicine that explores the use of light to control the pharmacological activity of drugs. Traditional pharmacology relies on the administration of drugs in a systemic manner, often leading to widespread effects throughout the body and potential side effects. Photopharmacology seeks to overcome these limitations by introducing light-responsive molecules into drug formulations, allowing for precise spatial and temporal control over drug activity. One of the key principles of photopharmacology is the use of photoswitchable molecules, which can change their structure and properties in response to specific wavelengths of light. These molecules can exist in two or more states, such as active and inactive, and can be toggled between these states using light. This means that one can selectively activate or deactivate drug molecules at

targeted locations within the body, minimizing off-target effects and enhancing therapeutic efficacy (Fig.1). Photopharmacology has promising applications in various medical fields, including neuroscience, oncology and drug delivery systems. For example, in neuropharmacology, light-sensitive molecules can be used to modulate the activity of specific neurons with high spatial precision, offering new insights into brain function and potential treatments for neurological disorders. In oncology, photopharmacology allows for the targeted delivery of anticancer drugs to tumor sites, reducing damage to healthy tissues and improving patient outcomes. A related field is optogenetics which combines genetics, optics and neuroscience to control the activity of specific cells in living organisms using light-sensitive proteins called opsins. This tool allows researchers to selectively manipulate the electrical activity of neurons or other cells with high spatial and temporal precision.

Fig. 1 Concept of photopharmacology.

The key component of optogenetics is the use of genetically encoded light-sensitive proteins, such as channelrhodopsins and halorhodopsins, which can be introduced into target cells using gene transfer techniques. These opsins respond to different wavelengths of light, allowing researchers to either stimulate or inhibit the activity of cells by shining light on them.

The phototherapeutic window

This refers to a range of wavelengths within the electromagnetic spectrum that is particularly effective for therapeutic applications involving light. This window is characterized by the optimal penetration of light into biological tissues while minimizing damage to surrounding cells and structures. In phototherapy, such as photodynamic therapy and photopharmacology, the phototherapeutic window is crucial for achieving therapeutic effects without causing harmful side effects. Different tissues and molecules within the body have varying absorption and scattering properties for light of different wavelengths. For instance, photosensitising drugs are injected into the body in photodynamic therapy, followed by a light irradiation, which releases free radical oxygen species to kill cancer cells. For this technique, light of wavelength 700–900 nm is the best as this range consists of relatively low-energy photons compared to UV photons; hence, it is not damaging to the tissue. Similarly, for the practical application of photopharmacology, the light used for switching the molecules between isomer states should be within the phototherapeutic window. However, the well-known azobenzene molecules switch at a wavelength of 340 nm in the ultraviolet (UV) range, which is known to be damaging to cells. Hence, the development of novel photoswitchable molecules that switch in the visible (>400 nm) and near-IR (>700 nm) ranges is fundamentally important (Fig. 2).

Visible/near-IR active photoswitches

This category of photoswitches is designed to have specific absorption in the visible/near-IR wavelength. In the case of photoswitches, there exists a trade-off between the wavelength of light used to switch a molecule and the stability of its photoiso-

mer. Specifically, as the wavelength shifts towards the red region, the stability of the molecular form obtained through light tends to decrease to the order of seconds or microseconds. Therefore, designing photoswitches capable of switching with longer-wavelength light while maintaining long photoisomer stability presents a significant challenge. Azobenzenes that switch at higher wavelengths have indeed been synthesized; however, in most cases, they revert back to their original state within microseconds. One approach to address this issue is by introducing substitutions on the benzene rings, which can slow down the thermal back isomerization process [1].

Fig. 2 Design of visible/near-IR active photoswitches.

Another approach is to replace benzene of azobenzene with a “heteroaryl” segment that has unique electronic properties. Specifically, photoswitches having a five-membered heteroaryl motif have distinct photophysical properties, steric profile and molecular geometries. Many drug molecules contain five-membered heteroaryl motif and hence their photoswitchable analogue can be used in photopharmacology, provided that the photoswitch isomerised by visible light irradiation. Previously, pyrrole, pyrazole, imidazole, isoxazole, triazole and thiophene were considered five-membered heteroaryl motifs for the development of photoswitches. Recently, we have developed a novel class of photoswitch based on phenylazothiazole scaffold that undergoes reversible isomerization by visible light [2].

The photoswitch has very different spectral characteristics, such as red-shifted absorption maximum wavelength and well-separated absorption bands for its trans and cis isomers, compared to conventional azobenzene as well as other heteroaryl azo compounds. Substituents at ortho and para positions to the phenyl ring of the photoswitch resulted in further shift to longer wavelength with absorption maximum up to 460 nm. These photoswitches showed excellent photostationary distributions of trans and cis isomers with high thermal half-lives up to 6.6 hours.

Promising biological applications

The field of photopharmacology demonstrated several applications at research level, such as restoring vision, antibiotic resistance, reduced side effects of chemotherapeutic agents and diabetes. Drugs that inhibit the production of microtubules make up a major class of chemotherapies, but, as with many cancer drugs, their powerful effects lead to severe side effects, which can limit dosages. Combretastatin A-4 (CA4) is one such drug; however, their photoswitchable analogue inhibits microtubules only when light is shone. The photoswitchable CA4 can exist in cis and trans isomers of the drug, and only cis isomer effectively binds to microtubule and becomes 250 times more toxic to cancer cells than the trans isomer [3]. This study used blue light to con-

trol the drug action. However, it can be derivatized to switch in the visible region. A clinical translation may be possible, where a drug is provided in an inactive, non-toxic form and then locally induce its toxicity by light irradiation. In summary, the field of photopharmacology is still too early to assess the prospects of its potential in actual therapeutic benefit. The field is still in its infancy but starting to grow [4].

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Leveraging Artificial Intelligence-based Algorithm and AI-inspired Knowledge to Improve Material Strength

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Presently a postdoctoral researcher at the NIMS, Japan, he obtained his doctorate from the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi, India in November 2021. His expertise lies in machine learning, alloy design, thermomechanical processing, microstructure, and mechanical characterization of metallic materials, including high entropy alloys and Ni-based superalloys. His ongoing research is dedicated to the design of superalloys and the optimization of their heat treatment routes, employing artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques.

Introduction

Superalloys, such as Ni-based alloys, are used in extreme environments (e.g., in aerospace engines and turbines) due to their high-temperature strength, corrosion resistance, and fatigue resistance. Increasing their strength is vital for safety, efficiency, extended service life, and enhanced performance in critical high-temperature applications. Originating in the 1940s, modern “superalloys” emerged in the 1980s, with ongoing research focusing on optimizing alloy compositions, metalworking techniques, and heat treatments. Extensive studies highlight the influence of heat treatment on mechanical properties, with particular emphasis on refining aging treatments to enhance superalloy performance. Achieving enhanced strength in superalloys requires to optimize conditions during solution heat treatment and aging. Selecting the suitable

temperature for aging treatment is crucial for high-temperature alloys. As new alloys emerge, it is crucial for manufacturers to determine optimal aging schedules to enhance properties. There is a strong demand for methodologies to effectively optimize aging schedules for these alloys. Recently, a novel method called non-isothermal ageing (NIA) has been devised to improve the mechanical properties of various alloys, including Fe-Cu₃ and Al-Zn-Mg alloys. We introduce AI-inspired methodologies and discuss our approach to this issue using a Ni-Al binary alloy (Ni-19.11 at. % Al) with the γ/γ' two-phase microstructure, serving as a model for Ni-based superalloys. We have developed a computational workflow in Materials Integration by network technology (MInt), our original material design system, for high-throughput prediction of 0.2% proof stress with varied aging treatment scheduling.

Fig. 1 Integration of AI-based search algorithm and MInt simulation system.

Concept: Integration of AI-based Isothermal aging benchmark Algorithm and Simulation System

We used Monte Carlo tree search (MCTS), an AI-based search algorithm, in combination with the MInt simulation system to design NIA schedules, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The Python implementation MCTS was employed, balancing search exploration vs. exploitation. NIA schedules were represented as nodes in a shallow tree, with each node representing a possible end temperature assignment for a schedule step. The tree starts empty and gradually expands towards promising areas of the search space using the Upper Confidence Bound (UCB) score. Each iteration involved selection, expansion, simulation, and backpropagation steps. We also computed conventional isothermal heating for comparison with the NIA schedules. The MInt system, utilized for forward calculations in these alloys, is a computational workflow we developed. It simulates microstructure evolution and evaluates high-temperature strength for various alloys. We established the search space conditions, setting the total aging scheduling time to 10 minutes. This means we aimed to design NIA scheduling that surpasses the isothermal aging benchmark within this 10 minute time frame.

Fig. 2 (a) Sketch map of NIA scheduling, (b) γ' phase fraction, (c) γ' size and (d) 0.2% proof stress as a function of aging time [Nandal et al. *Sci Rep* 2023, **13**, 12660].

The isothermal aging benchmark for the Ni-19.11 at.% Al alloy with γ/γ' two-phase microstructure was determined using the MInt system. The highest 0.2% proof stress was found for isothermal aging at 642° C, yielding a value of 784.48 MPa. This benchmark was established for a fixed time of 10 minutes at a service temperature of 725° C. The optimal isothermal aging temperature was identified as 642° C. The resulting 0.2% proof strength benchmark stands at 784.48 MPa and is henceforth denoted as the isothermal aging benchmark. It is important to highlight that this benchmark value was assessed within a precise range of 1° C.

Optimizing the NIA schedules using AI

We considered 12 independent MCTS trees with 135 iterations each due to computational constraints. Figure 2a shows the iteration curve for finding the best five NIA schedules. Notably, these five trees include various types of NIA that surpassed the isothermal aging benchmark. Remarkably, we identified 110 NIA schedules out of 1620 that outperformed the benchmark. Figures 2b-d compare microstructure characteristics and 0.2% proof stress of the top five NIA schedules against the isothermal aging benchmark. Figure 2d illustrates the precipitation hardening process during isothermal aging and NIA up to 10 minutes. In isothermal aging, the 0.2% proof stress gradually increases over time, as seen by the grey dotted line in Figure 2d. However, with NIA at 700° C for one minute, there is a significant increase in 0.2% proof stress within the first 2 minutes (1 min at 700° C and 1 min cooling to 550° C), as shown in Figure 2d. This rapid increase can be attributed to the growth of γ' precipitates to 40 nm in 2 minutes (Figure 2c), leading to a phase fraction rise to 56%. Subsequently, the size stabilizes, with the fraction increasing from 56% to 57.7% (Figure 2b). The microstructural observations of a top NIA case (0.2% proof stress 789 MPa) show the highly stable nature of γ' precipitates. This suggests that the aging temperature is relatively low in later NIA stages (Figure 2a), resulting in weaker coarsening kinetics and increased stability of the precipitates at lower temperatures.

Fig. 3 (a) Aging heat treatment scheduling of isothermal benchmark, AI-assisted maximum proof stress NIA and AI-inspired expert-design NIA and (b) variation of 0.2% proof stress as a function of second step temperature [Nandal et al., 2023].

AI-Inspired expert-designed NIA

The AI-based top 5 NIA typically involves two steps: 1. High-temperature, short-time aging; and 2. Low-temperature, long-time aging. We questioned the necessity of the small and complex temperature changes in Step 2. Hence, we designed a simpler two-step aging: 1-minute isothermal aging at 700 °C, followed by cooling to a lower temperature, and 8-minute isothermal aging at that lower temperature. This new approach, termed AI-inspired expert-designed NIA schedule, aims for a higher 0.2% proof stress while simplifying the process. We examined the optimal temperature for the second step between 525 – 575 °C to achieve the highest 0.2% proof stress and efficient increase of the γ' phase fraction (Figure 3a). The optimal second-step temperature was determined to be 555 °C, yielding the maximum 0.2% proof stress (Figure 3b, black dotted arrow). Our new two-step aging with this optimal temperature outperformed both the isothermal aging benchmark (grey dashed lines) and the AI-derived best NIA (black dotted lines).

In conclusion, our study developed a pipeline to optimize NIA schedules for maximizing 0.2% proof stress at 725 °C in the Ni-Al binary alloy with $\gamma - \gamma'$ two-phase microstructure. This pipeline included a computational workflow predicting 0.2% proof stress

in MInt and MCTS, an AI algorithm efficiently finding NIA routes. MCTS identified 110 NIA schedules surpassing the isothermal aging benchmark in 0.2% proof stress. Based on the essence of the AI-discovered NIA as uncovered through analysis, we have introduced a new concept of two-step aging. This process involves an initial 1-minute isothermal aging stage at 700 °C, followed by a subsequent cooling to a lower temperature, succeeded by an 8-minute isothermal aging period at this lower temperature. Through our investigations, we determined the optimal lower temperature for this second step to be 555 °C, specifically for the alloy under consideration. Subsequent validation has demonstrated that this AI-inspired NIA surpasses the previously identified best approach found through AI analysis. The design methodology, inspired by AI-found solutions and the new two-step aging concept, is promising for Ni-based superalloys with similar $\gamma - \gamma'$ two-phase microstructure.

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14th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2023

Conveners: Dr. P.K. Hashim, Dr. Abhijit Shrotri and Dr. B.G. Siddabasave Gowda, Hokkaido University, Japan

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) organized its 14th Annual Symposium on “Integrated Science for a Sustainable Society,” for the first time in northern Japan, in the campus of Hokkaido University, Sapporo, on November 10, 2023. The symposium featured a comprehensive day of interdisciplinary sessions covering a wide array of scientific and technological fields.

The symposium commenced with convener Dr. P. K. Hashim from the Hokkaido University providing a brief introduction to the event. Dr. Sunil Kaul, Chairman of ISAJ, in his welcome, offered insights into the organization’s history. The inaugural address was given by His Excellency Mr. Sibi George, the Ambassador of India to Japan, delivered through a recorded video. He highlighted the recent history of India-Japan diplomatic relations, emphasizing the collaborative efforts in scientific research.

Executive Vice President Prof. Aya Takahashi and Prof. Kuniharu Ijro, Director of RIES at Hokkaido University, shared perspectives on the enduring relationship between Hokkaido University and researchers from India. Prof. Nobuyuki Tamaoki of Hokkaido University was honored with the ISAJ Mentorship Award, acknowledging his exceptional mentorship of numerous Indian students over the past two decades. The opening session concluded with remarks from Dr. Alok Singh, Vice Chairman of ISAJ.

The symposium encompassed a wide range of research topics in four main sessions, presented by 3 plenary and 14 invited speakers (notably, about half of the invited speakers were emerging young scientists), as well as 43 poster presentations, showcasing the depth and breadth of scientific exploration: thermoelectric oxides, nutraceutical and pharmaceutical potential of honeybee propolis, application of nanomaterials, remote sensing in civil engineering, next-generation mRNA vaccines against infectious diseases and cancer, plant transcription factor engineering for our sustainable future, innovative environmental technologies for garbage, green tea leaves, Himalayan tectonics, biobased C4 chemicals, arti-

ficial intelligence/machine learning, ultra-sensitive virus detection, design and synthesis of piezochromic materials, alternative materials to plastics, development of a DNA aptamer, Visible-Light photo-switches, as well as a luncheon seminar on a very important topic of chances and pitfalls of aiming at an academic career in Japan. The poster presentation session provided a platform for sharing research findings and fostering discussions.

There were about a 100 participants in all, from institutions all over Japan, including the University of Tokyo, National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS) Tsukuba, Hokkaido University, Kyoto University, Toyo University, Shizuoka Institute of Science and Technology, Chitose Institute of Science and Technology, Tokyo Medical and Dental University, Shimane University, United Nations University, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), iCONM Kawasaki, Nagaoka University of Technology, Toyama Prefectural University, and others.

The symposium concluded with poster presentation awards recommended by a panel of experts from the diverse fields of science and technology. The recipients were Dr. Vickey Nandal (National Institute for Materials Science), Ms. Vanshita Sharma (Toyama Prefectural University) and Ms. Nusaiba Madappuram Cheruthu (Hokkaido University). Each recipient received a cash prize of 20,000 yen, acknowledging their exceptional contributions to the symposium’s scientific discourse and innovative research endeavors.

The symposium ended with co-convener Dr. Abhijit Shrotri (RIES, Hokkaido University), extending heartfelt thanks to the participants for their contributions to a successful event. He also outlined a few plans for the next installment of the symposium, setting the stage for future collaborations and advancements in the field of science and technology. The event concluded on a high note, with anticipation and excitement for the continued growth and impact of the ISAJ Annual Symposium.

14th ISAJ Annual Symposium-2023

Ambassador of India H.E. Mr. Sibi George addresses via video recording

Opening address by Convener Dr. P.K. Hashim

Address by Hokkaido University Vice President Prof. A. Takahashi

ISAJ Chariman and Vice-Chairman honor Prof. N. Tamaoki with Mentorship Award

Luncheon Seminar session!

Lively Poster session!

Poster presentation winners receive their awards.

Group picture of participants of the 14th Annual Symposium held at the Hokkaido University campus in November 2023.

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About ISAJ

The Indian Scientists' Association in Japan (ISAJ) is a Non-Profit Organization (NPO) aimed at networking and promoting Science and Technology Cooperation between India and Japan.

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